

HYBRID VERSION OF LINGUISTICS WITH THE HUMANITARIAN DISCIPLINES. PECULARITIES OF ETHNOLINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This thesis is devoted to the study of hybrid version of linguistics with the humanitarian disciplines. Furthermore, it investigates the study of ethnolinguistics to some extent, together with some of the distinct features and peculiarities of this very specialty.

Key words: humanitarian disciplines, ethnolinguistics, interdisciplinary approach, cultural diversity, language evolution, sociolinguistic variation, language revitalization.

Linguistics is a science about language, its social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of operation (activity) of specific languages, and historical development. It is the scientific study of language and its structure, including the analysis of language form, meaning, and context. This involves the study of phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, and discourse analysis. Linguists investigate how languages are structured, how they evolve and change over time, how they are acquired by individuals and communities, and how they are used in communication. The field of linguistics also encompasses sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, computational linguistics, and historical linguistics. Therefore, linguistics plays a crucial role in understanding the nature of human language and its complexity.

A hybrid version of linguistics and the humanitarian disciplines could be referred to as "humanitarian linguistics". This interdisciplinary approach would involve studying language within the context of humanitarian concerns, such as human rights, social justice, cultural diversity, and global development. It would involve a deep understanding of how language intersects with issues of access to education, healthcare, political participation, and the preservation of indigenous languages. In this field, linguists would work closely with professionals in humanitarian disciplines such as anthropology, sociology, psychology, international relations, and development studies. Together they would explore how language impacts the lives of individuals and communities, and how linguistic barriers can exacerbate humanitarian crises. This interdisciplinary approach could also involve studying the role of language in conflict resolution, peace-building, and the promotion of intercultural understanding. It could also address issues of language preservation, linguistic diversity, and the rights of minority language speakers. Overall, humanitarian linguistics would aim to create a more holistic understanding of the role of language in contributing to social, political, and economic development, and in addressing the needs of vulnerable and marginalized populations.

Moreover, hybrid linguistics can refer to the integrated study and analysis of multiple linguistic theories, methodologies, and approaches. It might involve combining traditional methods of linguistic analysis with computational methods, or integrating historical linguistics with sociolinguistics for a comprehensive understanding of language evolution and variation. Hybrid linguistics includes the exploration of the intersection between linguistics and other fields such as cognitive science, anthropology, or computer science to gain a more

holistic perspective on language and communication as well. Thus, hybrid linguistics seeks to bridge different linguistic disciplines and methodologies to offer a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of language and its various aspects.

Ethnolinguistics (sometimes called cultural linguistics) is an area of anthropological linguistics that studies the relationship between a language and the non-linguistic cultural behavior of the people who speak that language. Several controversial questions are involved in this field: Does language shape culture or vice versa? What influence does language have on perception and thought? How do language patterns relate to cultural patterns? These questions, which had been posed earlier by the German scholars Johann Gottfried von Herder and Wilhelm von Humboldt and their followers in the idealist-romanticist tradition, emerged again in the United States as a result of the discovery of the vastly different structure of American Indian languages, as delineated by the American anthropological linguists Edward Sapir and Benjamin L. Whorf. They noticed, for example, that Eskimo has many words for snow, whereas Aztec employs a single term for the concepts of snow, cold, and ice. The notion that the structure of a language conditions the way in which a speaker of that language thinks is known as the Whorfian hypothesis, and there is much controversy over its validity. Ethnolinguistics is a fascinating field that explores the relationship between language and culture. Here are some of the peculiarities and characteristics of ethnolinguistics:

1. Cultural Diversity: Ethnolinguistics examines the rich diversity of languages and cultures around the world. It explores how language is intertwined with the customs, traditions, and belief systems of different cultural groups.
2. Language Evolution: Ethnolinguists study how languages evolve over time within specific cultural contexts. They investigate the ways in which language change reflects social, historical, and environmental factors.
3. Sociolinguistic Variation: Ethnolinguistics is concerned with understanding how language varies within different social and cultural groups. This includes the study of dialects, sociolects, and other forms of linguistic variation.
4. Language and Identity: Ethnolinguistics explores the ways in which language is connected to individual and group identities. It investigates how language use contributes to the formation of cultural identity and group belonging.
5. Language Contact and Borrowing: Ethnolinguists study the impact of language contact and borrowing on the development of languages. They examine how languages influence one another through interaction and contact.
6. Ethnographic Research: Ethnolinguistics often involves ethnographic fieldwork, where researchers immerse themselves in a particular culture to study the language and its role in shaping the cultural practices and traditions of that community.
7. Endangered Languages: Ethnolinguistics is concerned with documenting and preserving endangered languages, as well as understanding the social and cultural implications of language loss.
8. Language Revitalization: Ethnolinguists often engage in efforts to revitalize and promote the use of endangered languages within their respective cultural communities.
9. Applied Ethnolinguistics: Ethnolinguistics has practical applications in areas such as language policy, education, and translation, where an understanding of the relationship between language and culture is essential.

Overall, ethnolinguistics offers a unique perspective on the intricate connections between language and culture, shedding light on the rich tapestry of human communication and social interaction.

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